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Innovation

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Curtain wall facades are structures that span multiple storeys, and are normally made of metal elements and glass surfaces that bear only their own weight and no other dead load weight from the building.

Evonik participates in EU-project

EU launches research project with the object to approach a zero energy Standard. Evonik participates with development of special surfactants and additives.

Evonik is participating in the recently launched EU-project EENSULATE*. The objective of the project is to dramatically improve the heat insulating properties of curtain wall facades on buildings to nearly zero energy standards. Through a consistent lightweight design, the retrofitting of existing curtain walls is enabled at competitive costs, even on older buildings. Curtain wall facades are structures that span multiple storeys, and are normally made of metal elements and glass surfaces that bear only their own weight and no other dead load weight from the building.

EENSULATE is based on a highly insulating single-component foam, which is used in the cavities of the metal elements, and a vacuum-insulated double glazing with a multi-functional thermo-sensitive coating. The new concept will eventually be tested in real buildings following a development and prototype test phase.

Evonik is participating in EENSULATE through the Comfort & Insulation Business Line of its Nutrition & Care Segment. The business line develops specialty surfactants and additives to give insulating foam the advanced properties necessary for function, processing and storage. Evonik's innovation agency (CI-IPM-IA) assisted in scientific and commercial matters throughout the application process. The project which is scheduled to run 3.5 years, has received funding in the amount of €6.7 million from the EU's Horizon 2020 research program (grant agreement no. 723868).

* Development of innovative lightweight and highly insulating energy efficient components and associated enabling materials for cost-effective retrofitting and new construction of curtain wall facades.

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